

In the present paper, we report the synthesis of 1-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets, which on oxidation and cyclisation yielded the title compounds, viz. 3-arylimino-5-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines. These dithiazolidines have also been prepared by the oxidation of the corresponding 1-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]-5-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets and their biological activity studied.

Thus, the reaction (Scheme 1) of 6-methyl-2-aminobenzothiazole (1) with either cyanogen bromide followed by thiohydrolysis of the product 2 or with benzoyl isothiocyanate and alkaline hydrolysis of

- 6-8a; R = C₆H₅
 b; R = *p*-CH₃.C₆H₄
 c; R = *p*-CH₃.O.C₆H₄
 d; R = *p*-Cl.C₆H₄

Scheme 1

the product 3 resulted in the formation of identical 1-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]thiocarbamide (4). Compound 4 on benzylation with benzyl chloride afforded the benzylated product 5, which on reaction with appropriate aryl isothiocyanate gave 1-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-2,4-

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some 3-Arylimino-5-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines

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THE chemistry of 1,2,4-dithiazolidines has been of considerable interest to this research group and some of which possess various biological activities¹. 6-Methyl-2-aminobenzothiazole has attracted wide attention on account of its biological activities². Hence, it appeared of interest to combine the reactivity of -N=C-S- grouping of a benzothiazole and 1,2,4-dithiazolidine ring, with a view to synthesise certain 3-arylimino-5-benzothiazolyl-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines having potential biological activity.

NOTES

dithiobiurets (6). The product 6, on oxidation with molecular bromine got debenzylated and cyclised to 3-arylimino-5-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (7). The latter could also be prepared by oxidation of the corresponding 2,4-dithiobiuret (8), which in turn was obtained by reductive debenzylation of the related isodithiobiuret (6) with H₂S in pyridine/triethylamine and also by reduction of 7 under identical conditions. Following similar consecutive treatments, the remaining isodithiobiurets 6a, c, d afforded 7a, c, d and 8a, c, d respectively. The structure of 7 was confirmed by alternative route of synthesis [8→7] and also by ir and pmr spectral studies.

Biological activity: The title compounds were screened for their biological activity *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus* at concentration 2 and 5 mg ml⁻¹ in nutrient agar media following the Ditch-plate method⁴. Compound 7c inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* at the concentration of 5 mg ml⁻¹. The rest of the compounds were not significantly active.

Experimental

Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian A-60D spectrometer (90 MHz).

1-[2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolyl]thiocarbamide (4).
Method A: 6-Methyl-2-aminobenzothiazole (1; 8.2 g, 0.05 mol) was dissolved in acetone (20 ml) and reacted with benzoyl isothiocyanate at room temperature to afford the corresponding 1-[2-(6-methyl)benzo-

thiazolyl]-3-benzoylthiocarbamide (3). The latter, on hydrolysis with 10% NaOH yielded the related 1-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]-thiocarbamide (4), which was crystallised from ethanol, (5.6 g, 50%), m.p. 208° (Found: C, 48.41; H, 4.01; N, 18.85; S, 28.65. Calcd.: C, 48.43; H, 4.04; N, 18.83; S, 28.69%).

Method B: Ethereal solutions of 6-methyl-2-aminobenzothiazole (1; 8.2 g, 0.05 mol) and cyanogen bromide (5.3 g, 0.05 mol) were mixed, shaken well and kept for about 2 h. The reaction proceeded with the separation of the hydrobromide of 6-methyl-2-aminobenzothiazole. The cyanamide (2) formed remained in the ethereal solution and was isolated by filtration of the 6-methyl-2-aminobenzothiazole hydrobromide, followed by the evaporation of the ether. Crude *N*-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl] cyanamide⁵ (2) mixed with unchanged 1 was thus obtained. The cyanamide was separated by extracting the mixture with dilute alkali in which it was soluble and was reprecipitated from this alkaline extracts by just acidification.

N-[2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolyl]cyanamide (2; 2 g, 0.01 mol) was boiled with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide and hydrogen sulphide gas was passed through the solution for about 1 h. The residue obtained after evaporation of ethanol was washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (2 g, 85%), m.p. 208°.

Compound 4 was benzylated by Werner's method⁶ to yield 1-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide (5; 35%), m.p. 110°.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)					δ
				NH	C=N	CH ₂ -S	N-(C=S)-N	S-S	
6a	35	270	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂	3 200	1 680	1 410	1 200	—	2.24 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.69 (2H, s, S-CH ₂), 4.12 (1H, b, NH), 7.52 (13H, m, ArH)
6b	45	300	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂	3 185	1 675	1 405	1 190	—	2.20 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 2.24 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.72 (2H, s, S-CH ₂), 4.11 (1H, b, NH), 7.48 (12H, m, ArH)
6c	30	185	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ OS ₂	3 220	1 680	1 420	1 210	—	—
6d	35	315	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	3 200	1 675	1 420	1 200	—	—
7a	55	240	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂	3 250	1 620	—	—	420	2.30 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.51 (8H, m, ArH)
7b	70	220	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂	3 250	1 640	—	—	400	2.38 (6H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.35 (7H, m, ArH)
7c	65	220d	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS ₂	3 260	1 630	—	—	420	—
7d	60	215	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	3 260	1 640	—	—	450	2.32 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.52 (7H, m, ArH)
8a	65	160	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂	3 210	1 620	1 240	1 170	—	—
8b	60	180	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂	3 200	1 630	1 240	1 160	—	—
8c	60	130	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂	3 215	1 630	1 240	1 160	—	—
8d	65	220	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ S ₂ Cl	3 220	1 640	1 240	1 170	—	—

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

1-[2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolyl]-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiurets (6a-d): 1-[2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolyl]-5-*p*-tolyl-2-S-benzyliso-2,4-dithiobiuret (6b): An equimolar mixture of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (4.5 g, 0.03 mol) and 1-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]-2-S-benzylisothiocarbamide (9.4 g, 0.03 mol) in dry benzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The resultant mass obtained after the evaporation of excess solvent was washed with petroleum ether and treated with a small amount of ethanol to give a solid product, which was crystallised from ethanol as a white fluffy compound (6.3 g, 45.5%), m.p. 300° (Table 1).

3-Arylimino-5-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (7a-d). Method A: 3-*p*-Tolylimino-5-[2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl]imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (7b): Compound 6b (5 g, 0.011 mol) was made into a paste with a small amount of chloroform and then treated with molecular bromine in small portions with stirring until the colour of bromine persisted. The mixture warmed up considerably evolving fumes of benzyl bromide. It was allowed to stand for about 1 h and then thoroughly washed with diethyl ether. On trituration with ethanol the hydrobromide of oxidation product was separated. The hydrobromide on treatment with ammonia afforded the free base, which was crystallised from ethanol, (2.80 g, 70%), m.p. 220° (Table 1).

Method B: 1-[2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolyl]-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (8b; 2 g, 0.0054 mol) was treated with bromine in dilute ethanol (15 ml) with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for about 1 h and the hydrobromide of oxidation product was precipitated by the addition of excess of diethyl ether. The free base obtained by treating the hydrobromide with ammonia, was crystallised from ethanol, (7b; 1.39 g, 70%), m.p. 220°.

1-[2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolyl]-5-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (8a-d). From 6b: Compound 6b (3 g, 0.0065 mol) dissolved in 30 ml of pyridine triethylamine solution (1:6) was subjected to a stream of dry hydrogen sulphide for 5 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered, poured over crushed ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (1.45 g, 60%), m.p. 180° (Table 1).

From 7b: Compound 7b (2 g, 0.0054 mol) was warmed with an ethanolic ammoniacal sulphide solution (30 ml) and dry hydrogen sulphide was passed for about 1 h. It was then diluted and acidified to precipitate the product which was crystallised from ethanol, (1.41 g, 70%), m.p. 180°.

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